

Ms 10

Course catalogue
of capacity
building training

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Contributors

NAME	ORGANISATION
Marco Antonio Segovia Bifarini	CC
Ladeja Godina Košir	CC

Peer Reviews

NAME	ORGANISATION
Inazio Martinez de Arano	EFI
Andrea Violeta Arancibia	EFI
Zsófia Kunya	ÖMKi
Korinna Varga	ÖMKi

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Abbreviations

CE	Circular Economy
D	Deliverable
TWG	Thematic Working Group

Introduction to the project

BOOST4BIOEAST is a Coordination and Support Action funded by the European Commission developed to support the BIOEAST Initiative with the aim of empowering national stakeholders in the Central Eastern European and Baltic countries for the development of national bioeconomy action plans and to build long-lasting structures and spaces of dialogue for national and macro-regional cooperation. The project will enrich knowledge on the bioeconomy and stimulate related research and innovation across the macro-region.

1 Introduction

This Milestone No. 10 report “*Course catalogue of capacity building training*” was prepared within WP2 (Subtask 2.2.2) by Circular Change (CC) with the aim to provide a capacity building programme for the HUB and Thematic Working Group (TWG) Coordinators in order for them to acquire the necessary skills and competences to organise and animate national HUB and macro-regional TWG expert networks in the long run. This document contains, after a brief methodology explanation, **the rationale for capacity building** describing the main objectives, expected outcomes, and approach of the capacity building programme **and a capacity building catalogue** outlining the capacity building modules, topics, and preliminary scheduling. Based on this catalogue, two in-person trainings and a series of complementary online courses will be organised by CC with additional practical materials made available for the HUB and TWG Coordinators over the course of the BOOST4BIOEAST project.

2 Methodology

The capacity building rationale and catalogue are based on the project requirements of subtask 2.2.2. They also reflect insights from desk research and feedback from HUB and TWG Coordinators, ensuring relevance to the BOOST4BIOEAST and BIOEAST Initiative’s goals.

2.1 Desk research and stakeholder engagement

Desk research: was conducted to identify best practices and develop a tailored capacity-building framework. The main sources included the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform repository (<https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/knowledge-hub>), the BIOEAST Knowledge Platform (<https://bioeast.eu/knowledge-platform>), and the project’s Deliverable 2.1 *BIOEAST HUB Handbook* (Martinez and Arancibia, 2024). Additionally, studies - listed in the References chapter - on stakeholder engagement, hub and network governance, and the activities of existing HUBs and best practices were reviewed.

Stakeholder engagement: feedback from HUB and TWG Coordinators was collected through consultations during HUB Coordination Body Meetings and TWG Coordination meetings and dedicated online surveys between November and December 2024. The surveys aimed at collecting inputs from the Coordinators regarding which topics would be of relevance for their tasks and contexts, the skills (stakeholder engagement, stakeholder mapping, communication, etc) that they would need more attention to, and the preferred type of capacity building approach (workshops, peer learning sessions, case studies or lectures).

3 Capacity building rationale

3.1 Objective of the capacity building programme

Main objective

The goal of this capacity building programme is **to empower HUB and TWG Coordinators with the skills, knowledge, and tools needed to effectively manage their roles, empower, orchestrate and engage stakeholders tailored to their specific contexts** (public administrations, research organisations), thus contributing to the success of the BOOST4BIOEAST project.

Why it is important

On one hand, the establishment and continuous development of national bioeconomy HUBs serve to address both macro-regional goals and localized challenges. On the other hand, the implementation and continuous development of TWGs serve to strengthen sector-specific expertise, foster interregional collaboration, and drive actionable outcomes that support a sustainable transition to bioeconomy in the BIOEAST region. These roles are instrumental in advancing research and innovation, facilitating expert dialogue, and prioritizing the bioeconomy's development in the region.

The specific goals of the capacity building based on its target groups are to enable:

- 1) **HUB Coordinators** to effectively establish, operate, and maintain national bioeconomy HUBs, to implement national and local bioeconomy related initiatives, projects and tasks, and to inspire and stimulate the engagement of HUB stakeholders.
- 2) **TWG Coordinators** to effectively orchestrate their members and navigate their networks to implement bioeconomy related initiatives and tasks at macro-regional level, bringing forward research and innovation, facilitating expert dialogue, and steering priorities for the development of the bioeconomy in the macro-region.
- 3) **TWG and HUB Coordinators** to work in collaboration and harmony and enable synergies to enhance the overall outcome of both HUBs and TWGs.

These efforts align with the overarching objectives of the BOOST4BIOEAST project and adhere to the principles outlined in the D2.1 *BIOEAST HUB Handbook* developed in WP2.

3.2 Expected outcomes

The capacity-building efforts are designed to equip HUB and TWG Coordinators with the skills and tools necessary to achieve the following outcomes:

Reinforced capabilities in stakeholder engagement

- Mapping stakeholders effectively to identify key players, their needs and potential roles.
- Knowledge and capability in approaching and engaging stakeholders.
- Knowledge and capability in identifying and understanding which stakeholders to engage and how; to understand “what different stakeholders are looking for”.
- Coordinating, orchestrating, and aligning stakeholders towards common actions and shared goals.
- Increasing stakeholder commitment and engagement, fostering greater motivation and commitment among members, as well as managing their expectations.
- Encouraging proactivity in problem addressing and solving.
- Supporting collaboration and exchange with different external stakeholders (public administration, business, academia, media, etc.).
- Mediating different interests and ambitions of stakeholders and shaping a common vision.

Strengthened HUB value proposition, communication, and branding

- Crafting compelling value propositions that address the core question of stakeholders: “What is in it for me?” by emphasizing the importance, relevance, and impact of HUB and TWG value propositions in stakeholder engagement.
- Developing effective communication strategies to highlight HUB and TWG objectives and benefits of membership.
- Supporting branding guidelines (provided by APRE) to enhance visibility and foster trust among stakeholders.
- Communicating the benefits of participation and collaboration internally and externally to motivate, engage and retain stakeholders.

Improved meeting and communication efficiency and effectiveness

- Strengthening timekeeping and organizational practices for meetings.
- Streamlining communication processes, including timely reminders to obtain responses.
- Improving micromanagement of TWG/HUB tasks.
- Leveraging available resources and ensuring investment commitment across participating countries.

Enhanced knowledge for long-term operational existence of HUBs and TWGs

- Developing a robust vision to ensure the essential role of the HUB/TWG and shared vision with its members and key stakeholders.
- Leveraging available resources and ensuring business models of different financial contributions from different actors and across participating countries.
- Maintaining flexibility of the core project management team to adjust to upcoming challenges in our region and beyond by providing competencies needed for systemic change.
- Establishing mechanisms for continuous improvement based on monitoring of implemented activities and their impact, including the feedback of stakeholders, to ensure alignment with strategic goals and continuous adaptation to meet the needs of stakeholders and purpose of HUBs/TWGs.

3.3 Approach and delivery of the capacity building programme

The capacity building programme will include both **in-person and online training sessions**, supported by supplementary materials, toolkits, and a library of best practices, case studies, networks and frameworks.

A **blended and interactive learning approach will be used, integrating theory and practical learning** through:

- **Webinar and workshops:** interactive sessions focusing on specific skills such as stakeholder mapping and communication.
- **Case studies:** analysis of successful HUB/TWG initiatives for practical insights.
- **Peer to peer learning:** opportunities for Coordinators to share experiences and learn from one another.
- **Toolkits:** templates and resources for ecosystem mapping, stakeholder engagement, and action plan implementation, building upon D2.1 *BIOEAST HUB Handbook*.
- **Podcasts:** direct interaction with relevant experts and concrete guidelines for improving bioeconomy in case of assured collaboration with external partners.¹

3.4 Duties and responsibilities of participants

To maximize the benefits of the capacity building programme, participants must consider the following guidelines:

- **Actively participate** in all sessions, whether online or in person.

¹ Podcasts might be developed based on assured collaboration of external partners when possible. This will help strengthen communication, modernising and enhancing BIOEAST positioning.

- **Engage with HUB/TWG peers** during learning activities to foster collaboration and exchange of ideas and create communities that go beyond the capacity building programme.
- **Review and utilize the provided materials**, toolkits, and guidelines to reinforce learning.
- **Apply** the theoretical concepts to real-world scenarios and case studies to enhance practical understanding.
- **Provide feedback and insights** to develop and improve the program and contribute to shared learning experiences, with short evaluation questionnaires after each module (see section 3.5).

3.5 Feedback mechanisms and documentation of progress

To ensure the effectiveness and continuous improvement of the capacity-building programme, a structured evaluation will be implemented

The following feedback mechanisms will be used:

- **Pre- and post-training surveys** to assess practical application of knowledge.
- **Periodic check-ins** during the programme will be implemented to reinforce learning and ensure long-term impact.
- **Case studies** documenting best practices and success stories from the HUBs and TWGs will be collected.
- **Peer learning and exchange sessions** to facilitate continued knowledge sharing. These can be organised corresponding to HUB Coordination Body meetings and TWG Coordination meetings.
- **Exchange and communication platform** via existing project SharePoint.

Progress will be monitored during HUB Coordination Body meetings and TWG Coordination meetings.

3.6 Capacity building journal

During the capacity building programme, both live and online **sessions will be recorded. Written summaries, materials, and photos** will be compiled into a comprehensive **capacity building journal**. This journal will be a **“living document”** and will serve HUB and TWG Coordinators, as well as the BIOEAST community, not only as a useful resource during the project but as a lasting resource beyond the project's conclusion. The journal will be a good source of information in the evaluation process during and at the end of the capacity building programme. A dedicated team at CC will analyse feedback to improve future iterations.

4 Capacity building modules and timeline

The following catalogue presents the structure of the capacity building programme, including its modules, topics, and objectives. A preliminary timeline allocation is provided in section 4.2.

Interactive activities, tools, and resources will be finalized during the programme. Didactic and support materials will evolve iteratively, ensuring relevance and applicability. They will be prepared and shared before each session for better engagement. Continuous feedback from participants and facilitators will refine the content in real-time. HUB case studies and progress updates will integrate practical examples and best practices, keeping materials dynamic, context-specific, and aligned with stakeholders' needs.

4.1 Capacity building modules

The programme is divided into six thematic modules covering:

- **Module 1:** HUB and TWG roles
- **Module 2:** Stakeholder mapping and engagement
- **Module 3:** Strategic communication and stakeholder relations
- **Module 4:** Network governance, social capital, and transition brokers
- **Module 5:** Strengthening HUB and TWG operations
- **Module 6:** Enhancing long-term sustainability of HUBs and TWGs

4.1.1 Module 1: HUB and TWG roles

Objective: Define the core responsibilities of the HUBs/TWGs and their Coordinators.

Topics:

- € The role of the BIOEAST HUBs and TWGs.
- € The role of the Coordinators.
- € Synergies across HUBs and TWGs.

Interactive activities, tools and resources

- € Role playing scenarios and simulating HUB and TWG Coordination challenges.
- € Governance and structure mapping.
- € Responsibility alignment exercise.
- € Best practices and case studies of successful networks and platforms.
- € D5.2 *BIOEAST HUB Handbook* and Playbook.

4.1.2 Module 2: Stakeholder mapping and engagement

Objective: Equip Coordinators with tools to identify, prioritise, engage, and retain key stakeholders.

Topics:

a) **Stakeholder mapping**

- € Context and ecosystem mapping.
- € Identifying key topics and priorities.
- € Stakeholder and value chain mapping: identifying key stakeholders and their roles.
- € Prioritizing stakeholders: stakeholders' roles and impact.

b) **Understanding stakeholder engagement**

- € The importance of stakeholder engagement.
- € The role of stakeholder engagement in achieving HUB and TWG objectives.
- € What does it mean to be a HUB member?
- € How to onboard stakeholders and gain their commitment?

Interactive activities, tools and resources

- € Interactive stakeholder mapping workshops.
- € Ecosystem mapping exercise.
- € Templates and toolkits for stakeholder mapping activities (stakeholder prioritization models, etc.).
- € Stakeholder persona development exercise.
- € Case study and best practices.
- € D2.1 *BIOEAST HUB Handbook* and *Playbook*.

4.1.3 Module 3: Strategic communication and stakeholder relations

Objective: Equip Coordinators with skills to effectively communicate HUB and TWG activities, enhance stakeholder engagement, and maximize the visibility and impact of the HUB's and TWG's work.

Topics:

a) **Crafting and communicating value**

- € Building the HUB's/TWG's narrative through applied storytelling.
- € Crafting and communicating compelling value propositions.

b) **Long-term stakeholder engagement**

- € Branding and stakeholder retention strategies.

- € Managing turnover and avoiding stakeholder fatigue.
- € Strategies for maintaining long-term engagement and encouraging proactivity.
- € Aligning your message with stakeholders' needs and interests.

Interactive activities, tools and resources:

- € Role-playing exercises in storytelling and narrative-building.
- € Stakeholder persona development exercise.
- € Workshop on crafting effective value propositions.
- € Communication toolkit.
- € Case studies on successful communication and dissemination initiatives.
- € D2.1 *BIOEAST HUB Handbook* and Playbook.

4.1.4 Module 4: Network governance, social capital, and transition brokers

Objective: Strengthen the ability to align and coordinate stakeholders effectively and foster the brokering of a sustainable bioeconomy transition in the macro-region.

Topics:

- € Principles of network governance.
- € Building and leveraging social capital.
- € Role of transition brokers in fostering collaboration.
- € Coordinating and aligning stakeholders.

Interactive activities, tools and resources:

- € Governance simulations for stakeholder coordination.
- € Transition broker role-playing exercise.
- € Examples of successful initiatives in Europe and abroad.
- € Publications on network governance and transition brokers.

4.1.5 Module 5: Strengthening HUB and TWG operations

Objective: Strengthen HUB and TWG operations by aligning activities with strategic goals, fostering synergies among members, optimizing resource use, and capitalising on common opportunities.

Topics:

- € Defining HUB/TWG activities in alignment with strategic goals.
- € Designing stakeholder meetings and workshops.
- € Enhancing operational efficiency and task coordination.

- € Leveraging available resources for sustainable operations.

Interactive activities, tools and resources:

- € Planning templates for HUB/TWG events and activities.
- € Workshop on resource mapping and operational efficiency.
- € Event prototyping exercises.
- € Examples of successful membership engagement strategies.

4.1.6 Module 6: Enhancing long-term sustainability of HUBs and TWGs

Objective: To establish a sustainable and adaptable framework for HUBs and TWGs, ensuring their long-term impact, financial stability, and ability to address evolving regional challenges.

Topics:

- € Reinforcing the project's impact through outcomes and lessons learned.
- € Strategic vision and role development: strengthening the HUB/TWG mission to maintain relevance and influence.
- € Sustainable financial models and ensuring long term investment and commitment.
- € Continuous improvement and impact assessment.

Interactive activities, tools and resources:

- € Strategic Visioning Workshop to define long term goals.
- € Examples of successful models and strategies.
- € Case studies on successful platforms/HUBs that achieved long-term sustainability through self-funding models or secured continuous funding for their activities.
- € Long-term impact measurement toolkit and template.

4.2 Capacity building timeline

The capacity-building timeline includes nine virtual sessions and two in-person sessions shown in Table 1. Each session lasts up to 1-3 hours covering one module. The proposed time allocation in the table is preliminary. A more precise allocation will be defined based on the actual availability of HUB and TWG Coordinators and other parallel project meetings such as HUB Coordination Body and TWG Coordination meetings.

The in-person sessions will be organized corresponding to the BOOST4BIOEAST Annual Meetings in Bucharest and Zagreb. The peer learning sessions as well as additional feedback sessions can be organised in collaboration with HUB Coordination Body and TWG Coordination meetings.

Table 1. Time allocation for capacity building sessions

Month	Module and topic	Session type	Duration
April 2025	Kick-off session and Module 1: HUB and TWG roles and responsibilities	In-person Workshop	2 Hours
April-May 2025	Module 2: Stakeholder mapping and engagement	Virtual Workshop	2-3 Hours
May 2025	Module 3: Strategic Communication and Stakeholder Relations	Virtual Workshop	2 Hours
June 2025	Module 4: Network governance, social capital, and transition brokers	Virtual Workshop	2 Hours
June 2025	Follow-up and feedback: reinforce learning and provide additional support	Virtual Follow-Up Session	1-1.5 Hour
September 2025	Peer learning and sharing session	Virtual Discussion	2 Hours
October 2025	Module 5: Enhancing long-term sustainability of HUBs and TWGs	Virtual Workshop	2 Hours
November 2025	Midpoint evaluation and networking	Virtual Peer-to-Peer Learning	2 Hours
January 2026	Topic based on midpoint evaluation and networking	Virtual Workshop	2 Hours
February 2026	Module 6: Enhancing long-term sustainability of HUBs and TWGs	Virtual Workshop	2 Hours
March-May 2026	Module 6: Enhancing long-term sustainability of HUBs and TWGs	In-person Workshop	2 Hours

5 Conclusions

This capacity-building programme has been designed to equip HUB and TWG coordinators with the essential skills and knowledge to effectively engage, orchestrate, and manage stakeholder networks. Through interactive sessions and modules, participants will explore critical aspects of stakeholder engagement, communication, and collaboration.

The success of this programme relies on the proactive involvement of HUB and TWG Coordinators. Their active participation, contributions to feedback mechanisms, and commitment to knowledge exchange will be instrumental in strengthening these networks and driving impactful change. To ensure relevance and applicability, the programme content has been tailored to the readiness, expertise, and specific needs of HUBs and TWGs.

Moving forward, the insights gained and connections built through this programme will serve as a foundation for continued collaboration and capacity development. By leveraging these learnings, HUBs and TWGs will be better positioned to navigate the complexities of stakeholder engagement and accelerate the bioeconomy transition in the macro-region.

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www.bioeast.eu

korinna.varga@biokutatas.hu

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